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TREATMENT OF OIL AND GAS PRODUCED WASTEWATER BY DEVELOPING AND OPTIMIZING A PHOTOCATALYTIC METHOD

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Summary

The treatment of the produced wastewater immersed from the oil and gas industries is indispensable due to the current environmental awareness and strict regulations. It's also very challenging due to the large amounts of produced wastewater and its complex nature that cannot be treated effectively by traditional wastewater treatment technologies.

The employment of photocatalysis, based on advanced oxidation processes (AOPs), as an innovative, environmentally friendly, facile and cost effective technology shall provide the route of an effective treatment. The main purpose of this research is to optimize the factors influencing the photocatalytic degradation kinetics of the contaminants into the non-harmful by products, carbon dioxide and water.

For the aim of the proposed research, zinc oxide was chosen to be as the photocatalyst. It was synthesized and prepared by the sol-gel method followed by dip-coating on a fiber glass substrate to create *ZnO* thin film. To test the effect of the photoactivity of the prepared photocatalyst on the kinetics of the photo-degradation, two parameters were altered and observed, the catalyst concentration and post-heat treatment temperatures. The photocatalytic degradation process was experimented on methylene blue as the contaminant source, and UV rays as the light source. The experimental time was 480 minutes, where the varied absorbance of methylene blue upon degradation was monitored at an interval of 30 minutes.

The catalyst concentration was varied to attain these 5 values, 0.03, 0.07, 0.1, 0.2 and 0.6M of zinc oxide. This change investigated how influencing the catalyst loading was on its surface and in turn on the degradation efficiencies. Interesting results emerged showing that the catalyst of concentration 0.1M was found to have the highest degradation efficiency where it was 36% more than the lowest concentration (0.03M), and 10% more than the highest concentration (0.6M) rendering 0.1M as the optimum catalyst concentration to be used for the investigation of the annealing temperature.

Moving on, the application of four annealing temperatures, 250, 350, 450, and 550°C, were studied on the 0.1M *ZnO* catalyst to further illustrate the effect of post-heat treatment on the thin films structure and consequently the rate of degradation. As a result, annealing at 450°C showed the highest degradation kinetics and efficiency of 88.82%

Keywords: Produced wastewater, Advanced Oxidation Processes, Photocatalysis, Zinc oxide, Degradation efficiencies, Concentration, Annealing temperature.

Résumé

Le traitement des eaux usées produites par les industries pétrolières et gazières est indispensable en raison de la conscience environnementale actuelle et des réglementations strictes. En revanche, il est difficile de traiter efficacement les eaux usées exclusivement à l'aide des technologies traditionnelles puisque la quantité des eaux produite est énorme ayant une nature et composition complexe.

L'utilisation de la photocatalyse, une technologie innovante, écologique, basée sur des procédés d'oxydation avancés (AOP), fournira la voie d'un traitement efficace des eaux. L'objectif principal de cette recherche est d'optimiser les facteurs qui affectent la cinétique de la dégradation photocatalytique des contaminants en sous-produits non nocifs, le dioxyde de carbone et l'eau.

Pour le but de la recherche proposée, l'oxyde de zinc a été choisi comme photocatalyseur. Il a été synthétisé et préparé par la méthode sol-gel suivie d'un revêtement par immersion sur un substrat en fibre de verre pour créer un film mince de ZnO. Pour tester l'effet de la photoactivité du photocatalyseur préparé sur la cinétique de la photo-dégradation, deux paramètres ont été modifiés et observés: la concentration en catalyseur et les températures de post-traitement thermique. Le processus de dégradation photocatalytique a été expérimenté sur le bleu de méthylène comme source de contaminant et les rayons UV comme source lumineuse. La durée expérimentale était de 480 minutes, où l'absorbance variée du bleu de méthylène lors de la dégradation a été surveillée à un intervalle de 30 minutes.

La concentration du catalyseur a été modifiée pour atteindre ces 5 valeurs, 0,03, 0,07, 0,1, 0,2 et 0,6 M d'oxyde de zinc. Ce changement en concentration a montré comment influence-t-il sur la surface du catalyseur ainsi que sur l'efficacité de la dégradation.

Des résultats intéressants ont montré que le catalyseur de concentration 0,1M s'est avéré avoir l'efficacité de dégradation la plus élevée, étant 36% de plus que celle produite par la concentration la plus faible (0,03M), et 10% de plus que celle résultante de la concentration la plus élevée (0,6M). Donc, 0,1M est la concentration optimale du catalyseur à adopter pour l'étude de la température de recuit.

Ensuite, la variation de quatre températures de recuit, 250, 350, 450 et 550, a été étudiée sur le catalyseur 0,1 M de ZnO pour illustrer d'avantage l'effet du post-traitement thermique sur la structure des films minces et par conséquent le taux de dégradation. En conséquence, le recuit à 450°C a montré la cinétique de dégradation la plus élevée et l'efficacité de 88,82 %.

Mots-clés : Eaux usées produites, Procédés d'oxydation avancés, Photocatalyse, Oxyde de zinc, Efficacité de dégradation, Concentration, Température de recuit.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS & SYMBOLS

AOP	Advanced Oxidation Processes	2-PrOH	2-Propanol
BTEX	Benzene, Toluene, Ethylbenzene, Xylene	ZnO	Zinc Oxide
C	Concentration	TiO₂	Titanium Oxide
COD	Chemical Oxygen Demand	H₂O₂	Hydrogen Peroxide
E_g	Energy Gap	hν	Photon
HF	Hydraulic Fracturing	h⁺	Generated hole
MB	Methylene Blue	e⁻	Excited electron
MBR	Membrane Bioreactor	HO[•]	Hydroxyl Radical
MEA	Monoethanolamine	O₂⁻	Superoxide Ion
MF	Micro Filtration	HO₂⁻	Hydroperoxyl Ion
OAPEC	The Organization of Arab Petroleum Exporting Countries	HO₂[•]	Hydroperoxyl Radical
OSPAR	Oslo/Paris convention (for the Protection of the Marine Environment of the North-East Atlantic)	H⁺	Hydronium Ion
PAH	Polycyclic Aromatic Hydrocarbons	k	Rate Constant
PWW	Produced Wastewater	t	Time
SEM	Scanning Electron Microscope	°C	Degrees Celsius
TDS	Total dissolved solids	h	Hour
TOC	Total Organic Carbon	eV	Electron Volt
TSS	Total Suspended Solids	mg/l	Milligram/Liter
UF	Ultra Filtration	M	Mol/Liter
UV	Ultra Violet	μm	Micrometer
Vis	Visible	nm	Nanometer
ZAD	Zinc Acetate Dihydrate	mm	Millimeter

Introduction

Decades ago, the exploration of oil and gas took place and as it was spread worldwide, the production activities of it contributed to the generation of varieties of waste materials and wastewater, that are, produced water, injection water, oilfield water or brines, flood water, shale water and fracking water [1]. Produced water is the byproduct and largest stream of wastewater by volume generated by oil and gas production and is estimated to be around billion barrels per annum [2], it's the water trapped in hydrocarbon bearing formation strata and is brought up to the surface during gas and oil production [3].

Produced wastewater is often discharged into the sea, therefore many countries have imposed stringent regulations and standards to be obeyed. According to the Convention for the Protection of the Marine Environment of the North-East Atlantic (OSPAR Convention), the annual average limit for discharge of dispersed oil for produced water into the sea is 40 mg/L [4]. Accordingly, the treatment of produced water in an indispensable approach due to the enormous strict regulations imposed on its handling and disposal, as well as, for it contains huge amount of toxicants [5]. As the demand and production of oil and gas is continuing to increase globally due to population increase, the scarcity of freshwater supply is following the same trend too, therefore produced water can be a crucial source of fresh water after suitable treatment.

Numerous methods, physical and chemical, are designed for the treatment of PWW, but they can be of a very high cost, residual sludge, and are less innovative [6]. As for the biological treatment approaches, they weren't able to level up for the production of a polished water quality since the high complexity of produced wastewater and presence of highly toxic recalcitrant compounds, such as benzene, toluene, ethyl benzene, and xylene impeded their effectiveness [7].

Since our aim is not to extract, separate or remove, but to degrade and destruct, and due to the continuous drawbacks and inadequate treatment of the produced wastewater, the eyes have turned to the advanced oxidation processes, particularly photocatalysis.

The destruction of organic contaminants, and fast degradation rate are the main advantage of AOPs in contrast to other processes such as active carbon, thermal and membrane technologies, which transfer the contaminants from one phase to another [7].

This research has adapted the photocatalytic oxidation process to treat wastewater since it stands out amongst other technologies as it utilizes sunlight and operates at ambient conditions without needing high temperature or high pressure, and many recalcitrant organic contaminants can be degraded with and without the addition of chemical oxidants. Also, it's able to transform toxicants into less harmful species that are easy to remove which made this approach very attractive for PWW treatment.

This research consist of three chapters:

1st chapter: A general literature overview on produced wastewater from the oil and gas industries, its sources, treatment technologies, effect on animals and humans, composition and constituents.

2nd chapter: Photocatalysis, a brief history regarding it as well as its principles and fundamentals, its influencing parameter and choice of photocatalyst, contaminant and preparation method.

3rd chapter: Synthesis procedure of the zinc oxide thin films catalyst in the lab, the choice of materials, photocatalytic setup and experiments, techniques used along with the analytical method implemented, the alteration of catalyst concentration and post-heat treatment temperatures along with their effects on the photocatalytic degradation efficiencies on methylene blue.

1 A REVIEW ON UPSTREAM PRODUCED WASTEWATER

The huge amounts of produced wastewater generated through the upstream oil and gas industries have made it impossible to not acknowledge their existence. Accordingly, this chapter introduces the chemical composition and constituents of oil and gas produced wastewater and what factors affect them, the environmental footprint of PPW, and finally provides information on the recent treatment technologies imposed for the management of oil and gas PPW and its quality improvement.

1.1 Sources of Produced Wastewater and Possible Routes for its Usage

Produced wastewater is often generated during the production of oil and gas from onshore and offshore wells. It results from two processes in the oil and gas industry.

- First, during extraction, giving a mixture a seawater or fresh water that has been trapped for millions of years beneath hydrocarbons in porous reservoir medium. [8].
- Second, the injected water used to help the deep oil seep to the surface become ultimately a part of the produced wastewater as shown in Figure 1.1 [9].

Figure 1.1 Produced wastewater sources [9].

In gas fields, water injection is not used, which thus implies that the PW in a gas field is a mixture of formation water and condensed water [10]. Therefore, it could be derived that any water present in a hydrocarbon reservoir and produced at the surface with crude oil or natural gas is categorized as produced wastewater.

The amount of produced wastewater generated every year keeps increasing with the expansion of unconventional oil and gas development. Most of the volume of waste stream in oil and gas production operations on offshore platforms is produced water, and it represents 80% [11] of the residuals and wastes produced through the production of natural gas, globally it takes a share of 250 million barrels per day compared with around 80 million barrels of oil produced per day [12], giving it its take on that 80%.

The production volume of produced water is highly dependent on multiple factors, most importantly are what follows:

- The site-specific nature of the reservoir
- Extraction technologies
- The geographical location
- Most importantly, the age of the well.

The volume is prone to increase as the well ages and matures [13], to reach as low as 2% oil to 98% of PWW [14].

For this reason one can say that huge amounts of produced water are being generated, and there exist more than one route for them. The energy sector is a possibility since it reuses or recycles PWW for hydraulic fracturing (HF) of new wells in shale or tight oil plays. PWW reuse would reduce water sourcing to support HF, since they contain about 98% water [15]. In addition, most of the oil-rich countries are more or less water-stressed, meaning their interest in treating the PWW for increasing the supply of fresh water is very high.

As shown in Figure 1.2, it can contribute in the irrigation, industrial and municipal sectors [15], as well as livestock or wildlife watering and habitat, and needless to mention it can be injected underground for the increase of oil production [16].

Figure 1.2 Beneficial use of produced water within the energy sector (hydraulic fracturing) and outside the energy sector (irrigation, municipal, industrial, livestock), surface water discharge. [15]

1.2 Characteristics and Components of Gas and Oil Produced Wastewater

Produced wastewater is not a single commodity since it has a variable complex composition that is a mixture of dissolved and particulate organic and inorganic compounds. It's composition, physical and chemical traits are influenced by more than one factor including [17]:

- Geographic location of the field
- Production facility
- Seasonal variations,
- Type of hydrocarbon product being extracted
- The age and depth of the geological formation.
- Extraction method employed

The chemical characteristic of oil and gas have a significant effect on the quality of the PWW. This is for the reason that, the produced water has been in direct contact with the hydrocarbons bearing formation strata for ages and millennia, it therefore has some of the chemical characteristics of both the hydrocarbons and the formation nature.

Generally, the produced wastewater is considered saline, with a high quantity of TDS, TSS and TOC. It contains dissolved hydrocarbons, oils and gases (typically hydrogen sulfide and carbon dioxide) as smaller contaminants. PWW also contains a wide range of recalcitrant semi-volatile or volatile organic compounds (dispersed or emulsified) such as benzene, toluene, ethyl benzene, xylene (BTEX), polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), along with organic acids, and phenol that could cause a level of hardness resulting in calcium, magnesium, sulfates, and barium [18]. In addition to, the heavy metals and transformational byproducts resulting from chemical additives such as biocides and corrosion inhibitors that are used during drilling, fracturing and operating process of the well to improve the production operation [19]. The main components found in produced water, and their concentrations, were synthesized and categorized from several literatures and references to be summarized in Table 1.1.

Table 1.1 Main Components and Their Concentration Found in Produced Water

Parameter	Concentration(mg/l)	References	Parameter	Concentration(mg/l)	References
Major Parameters			Metals		
COD	1,220-2,600	[16,18]	<i>Na</i>	0-150,000	[17]
TSS	12-1,000	[16,18,19]	<i>Fe</i>	0.1-100	[16,18]
TDS	100-400,000	[5]	<i>Ti</i>	0.01-0.7	[16,18]
TOC	0-1500	[16,18]	<i>K</i>	24-4,300	[16,18]
Total Oil and Grease	2-565	[16,18,19]	<i>Zn</i>	0.01-35	[16,18]
Benzene	0.032-778.51	[20,21]	<i>Al</i>	0.4-410	[16,18]
Ethyl benzene	0.026-399.84	[20,21]	Ions		
Toluene	0.058-5.86	[20,21]	<i>Ca</i> ²⁺	0-74,000	[16,18]
Xylene	0.0258-1.29	[20,21]	<i>Mg</i> ²⁺	0.9-6,000	[16,18]
Total BTEX	0.39-35	[18]	<i>Cl</i> ⁻	0-250,000	[17]
Phenol	0.009-23	[16,18]	<i>SO</i> ₄ ²⁻	0-15,000	[16,18]
Corrosion Inhibitors	2-10	[19]	<i>HCO</i> ₃ ⁻	0-15,0000	[16,18]

1.3 Impacts of Produced Wastewater Discharge on Health and Environment

After stating the various and wide range of chemicals present in PPW, it's important to stress out what kind of an influence they would have on the surroundings taking into consideration the fact that produced water is often discharged into the environment/sea in offshore platforms, or injected into the soil in onshore platforms [16]. The environmental effect of produced wastewater disposal doesn't only take into account the volume; that when huge, could cause erosion and some serious ecosystem damage if the volume of the receiving body is limited, but it also depends mainly on the chemical composition of the PPW and their concentrations [10].

The compilation of the decent amount of monocyclic aromatics present in the BTEX group (benzene, toluene, ethylbenzene, xylene) little does it have any effect on the marine life for its highly volatile, and they degrade rapidly in seawater [20]. On the other hand, their influence on the human health is too transparent to be ignored. The BTEX group exhibits acute, chronic and somewhat deadly impacts on humans causing poisoning, inhalation issues, skin and neurological problems, leukemia, etc [21]. As for the marine life, it's mostly affected by the PAHs. PAHs are hydrophobic with high chronic toxicity and carcinogenic behavior that has various adverse effects on fish, hindering their reproductive and growth system [22]. Even though reinjection of produced water into production wells is an environmental alternative, yet the gas and oil industry somewhat finds it not always technically feasible. For the mentioned reason they turn to discharge, to dilute the pollute.

On the other hand, even this approach raises lots of concerns in the public eye due to the huge scientific vacuum in the oilfield chemistry that still has question marks about the exact specifications, composition and constituents of the PPW or the injected chemicals.

Figure 1.3 Produced water (PW) discharged from offshore oil and gas production will spread with oceanic currents, forming a continuously diluting plume that exposes to the components of PW [23].

1.4 Treatment Technologies of the Oil and Gas Produced Wastewater

The increased environmental awareness amongst the public eye has left the oil and gas industries subject to try and fit to the legislations. Accordingly, the treatment technologies must be highly effective and robust to be able to remove the various contaminants including solid particles and organics from the oily water to put it into beneficial use. Due to the complex and strong nature of the PWW, basic phase separation techniques are more or less ineffective [5], so the need of series of unit processes for the removal of suspended solid particles, oil and grease, dissolved and undissolved organics, gases and metals, is significant. The combinatory treatments involving physical and/or biological and chemical treatments are present in the three main stages PWW undergo, that are pre-treatment (primary), main treatment step (secondary), and final polishing treatment step (tertiary) [9]. A common form of wastewater treatment plants is similar to the one shown in the Figure 1.4.

Figure 1.4 Treatment processes of oilfield produced water [10].

The primary treatment, i.e. the pre-treatment, is done to remove large oil droplets, solid particles and air bubbles with lower density than water from PWW, through physical separation such as settling and flocculation tanks, and centrifuges.

Due to the fact that the pre-treatment on its own is not enough for the reuse of the PWW since dissolved organics and sludge will still be present, we move on to the secondary treatment, i.e. the main treatment step. This step employs both physical and biological technologies for the removal of much smaller oil droplets and dissolved components. The technologies used are floatation, adsorption, membrane separation; filtration (ultra and micro) and the recent development that is membrane bioreactor (MBR). Membrane separation with its various techniques offers a higher quality and less sludge formation.

Microfiltration (MF) has a pore size ranging from 0.1–10 μm that allows the movement of waters and retention of most, but not all, bacteria, colloidal particles and viruses [24] and according to Chen et al. [25], the oil and grease value reached $< 5\text{mg/l}$ when microfiltration was conducted. As for ultrafiltration (UF), it has a smaller pore size, 0.01 – 0.1 μm , so consequently it offers a complete retention of molecules and higher treatment efficiencies. On the other hand, it's no surprise that MBR offers the highest removal efficiencies in the means of filtration since it combines the biological techniques that allow biomass conversion of organisms, and the filter beds that simultaneously separate them from the water.

Last but not least, the tertiary treatment; i.e. the polishing step. It involves additional steps for the removal of ultra-small oil droplets, dissolved organics and gases, as well as turbidity and metals through chemical treatments. It involves advanced oxidation processes AOPs that aim to degrade and mineralize most of the organic contaminants improving the quality of the water prior discharge and use.

The PWW contains high amounts of BTEX that are readily ever degraded by just any radicals. From this point, the need for the novel, cost effective and efficient technique, that is AOP, has been aroused. AOPs provide the contaminants with an environment supported by strong hydroxyl radicals, so they have no choice but to completely oxidize, degrade and mineralize to less harmful species that are CO_2 and H_2O .

Advanced oxidation technologies could be classified as follows [10]:

- Ozone-mediated process (Ozonation).
- Photocatalytic oxidation process.
- Fenton and Photo-Fenton process.

This study will examine the efficiency and performance of the innovative novel route of advanced oxidation processes, which is photocatalysis, in degrading contaminants and improving the overall quality of water.

2 PHOTOCATALYSIS: AN INNOVATIVE OXIDATION TECHNOLOGY FOR TACKLING CONTAMINANTS

Chemical industries have contributed in the evolvement of the world, but they also have introduced a series of toxicants through different activities into the world. This has put some serious red flags and harms on human health and ecosystem where the corresponding pollutants are of danger to the environment and existence of certain livings.

On top of that, population growth is following an exponential trend, supply on clean water is of a decline, and the demand is highly increasing as the years pass, therefore the situation is of need to be managed and controlled. Most of the countries, worldwide, suffer from a shortage of this crucial source and a difficulty in supplying the sectors with aquifers, this huge imbalance has led the water reuse and treatment to be a priority for conserving water.

To tackle this issue, studies and researches have been made to combat this environmental struggle, where several treatment technologies and methods were applied. Photocatalysis controls the environmental pollution worsening throughout the years. It offers an efficient, inexpensive, stable and clean method to reuse, recycle and provide a source of uncontaminated water.

The main advantage it has over other methods, that made it very eye-catching, is the fact that it doesn't transfer the recalcitrant organics, inorganic ions and other contaminants into dangerous by-products that may hold further damage, but it transforms them into nontoxic wastes. Not only that, but also its ability to use sunlight as a main source of energy rendering it as a renewable and ecofriendly technique with lower costs compared to other technologies.

In the chapter, routes related to photocatalysis will be intercepted, starting with the history of this technology. Also, its principles and fundamentals will be widely discussed and illustrated as well as the system's mechanism and elements influencing photocatalysis. And finally, the types and choice of semiconductor, contaminant and preparation technique to be used in this research

2.1 Brief History of Photocatalysis

The concept of photocatalysis dates back to 1839 to the findings of Alexander-Edmond Becquerel who reported for the first time the photovoltaic conversion of light into electricity [26]. Decades later, in 1911, the German chemist Dr. Alexander Eibner incorporated this concept of photocatalysis in his research of the illumination of zinc oxide (ZnO) on the bleaching of the dark blue pigment, Prussian blue [27].

The relevancy of photocatalysis faded through decades due to the absence to practical experiments till some researchers actively started conducting surface studies on photocatalysts such as ZnO and TiO_2 the 1970s when the Arab Petroleum Exporting Countries (OAPEC) was embargoed. This has put some serious danger on scarcity of oil and the need for alternative energy resources has increased progressively. These threatening economic time periods have led to the existence of the opportunity of a world where clean hydrogen could be produced thanks to two Japanese researchers, Fujishima and Honda. In 1972, who thought on the possibility of using sunlight as the energy source and conducted the photolysis of water using a semiconductor electrode (TiO_2) in a photoelectrochemical cell [28].

Reaching the last couple of years where according to Ren et al. [29], semiconductor materials have been utilized as a photocatalyst for the treatment of both air and water, mineralizing organic toxins.

Therefore, it seems clear that photocatalysis, along its already centennial history, has acquired knowledge from very different times and researchers and has evolved to become a technology, which holds the promise of many environmentally friendly approaches to balance the societies' demands.

2.2 Principles and Fundamentals

Photocatalysis is a photo-induced reaction, which utilizes light, and is accelerated by the presence of a catalyst, that is the semiconductor. As simple as it is, and even though there is no scientific consensus as to a proper definition of photocatalysis, it could be generally used to describe a process that employs light, i.e. photo, to help activate a certain substance, that is the catalyst, which only interferes in altering the kinetics and not the thermodynamics of the chemical reaction to fasten it, without actually being altered or chemically transformed itself [30]. Photocatalysis cannot take place in the absence of either one of the following three parameters:

- Source of light.
- Photocatalyst.
- Contaminant.

The photocatalytic reactions can be categorized into two types on the basis of appearance of the physical state of the catalyst and substrate.

- Homogenous: is when both the photocatalyst and the reactant exist in the same phase and the photocatalyst is mostly a transitional metal such as iron [31].
- Heterogeneous: is when the photocatalyst and reactant are present in different phases and the photocatalyst is a semiconductor [32].

Both types of catalysts have a common outcome that is the hydroxyl radicals. They are highly reactive and nonselective, they degrade all organic matter present in water and can be used to remove many different compounds at the same time.

This provides complete mineralization of organics into carbon monoxide, water and inorganic salts [33]. Therefore, it's of a high significance in the approach of treating water to reach an optimum quality taking into account the importance of being environmentally friendly and of low-cost.

Heterogeneous photocatalysis is the most frequently used technique has been more appealing than homogenous photocatalysis. This is for the reason that, even though the homogenous photocatalytic system is well studied and it has been reported to be a promising method for wastewater treatment, but the ions remain in the solution at the end of the process in homogeneous photocatalytic reactions, and till now its removal is very challenging [34]. Whereas in the heterogeneous photocatalysis, one can easily separate the catalyst material after application and it can be reused. The semiconductor photocatalyst is mainly known through its photoactivity in UV and visible light, inertness, nontoxicity and low cost.

The energy difference between the valence band and the conduction band are known as the band gap (E_g). When the semiconductor catalyst gets illuminated with photons of energy greater than or equal to its band-gap energy in the presence of organic species, phases shown in Figure 2.1 occur

Figure 2.1 Schematic illustration of the basic principle of semiconductor photocatalyst [35].

- First, an electron absorbs this energy and is promoted from the valence band (VB), to the conduction band (CB), leaving behind a positive hole and by which creating the photo-generated pair e_{cb}^-/h_{vb}^+ .
- Second, the excited electrons and positive holes split and migrate from the bulk to the surface of the semiconductor and get trapped in the metastable state.
- Third, the electrons have a strong reduction energy capable of reducing an acceptor. For example, dissolved oxygen can be adsorbed on the surface of the photocatalyst and reduced to superoxide ions that in turn form hydrogen peroxide and lastly hydroxyl radical to degrade pollutants to CO_2 and H_2O . While the holes have a strong oxidative potential to either degrade the pollutant directly to CO_2 and H_2O or oxidize electron donors, such as water, to generate hydroxyl radicals [36].

Reduction Reactions

Oxidation Reactions

Figure 2.2 A scheme showing the reduction process in photocatalysis [37].

Figure 2.3 A scheme showing the oxidation process in photocatalysis [37].

It's important to stress out that if the oxidation and reduction reactions don't occur simultaneously, the electrons will accumulate in the conduction band and this may promote the electron-hole recombination and consequently affect the degradation procedure.

2.3 Main Parameters Influencing the Photocatalytic Degradation Efficiency

The efficiency and degradation rate of the wastewater treatment by photocatalysis are governed by many factors, the most significant ones include the surface area, light wavelength and intensity, and catalyst dosage. [38]. Therefore, for the sake of implementing a decent photocatalysis with an optimum activity of the semiconductor, these factors are to be addressed.

2.3.1 Light Intensity and Wavelength

The photocatalytic reaction rate depends on the light absorption by the semiconductor. As more light irradiations of high intensities fall on the surface of the catalyst, the electron-hole pair formation is promoted, more hydroxyl radicals are consequently produced and therefore the rate of the reaction is enhanced [39]. But at higher light intensities, the rate becomes independent of the intensities for the following reason.

According to Lee et al. [40], at a certain point, there will be more photons per unit time and unit area but constant active sites and the surface of the catalyst will be packed with the contaminants and thereby limiting the mass transfer, leading to the conclusion of, in this case, as high as the light intensity gets, it will not have an impact on the rate anymore that will remain constant

As for the wavelength, the band gap energies of the most famous semiconductors oxides, ZnO and TiO_2 , that are respectively 3.37 eV and 3.2 eV, lie in the UV-A region [41]. Therefore, the greater part of photocatalytic degradation studies have been carried out between the wavelengths 320-380 nm

2.3.2 Surface Area and Morphology

Recent studies have been focusing on the nanostructure of the photocatalysts [42] since they offer different physiochemical properties from bulk catalysts and a higher surface area. Accordingly, since the shape affects the surface area as well as the surface area to volume ratio, it affects the rate of reaction by minimizing or maximizing the contact area between the reactants and the photocatalyst and this was proven through a study implemented by Assi et al. [43]. Thus, the smaller the particle size, the larger the surface area, the higher concentration of active sites and therefore the redox reactions are of an increase.

2.3.2 Catalyst Concentration

The effect induced by the addition of the catalyst and its mass on the degradation rate has been investigated by lots of researchers including Hayat et al. [44]. In principle, higher concentrations of catalyst provide higher relative numbers of active sites and thickness thus, providing higher rates of hydroxyl and superoxide radicals generation as well, which facilitates the degradation of the organic pollutants.

The degradation rate increases with catalyst loading till it reaches a saturation level where it starts to decrease upon further addition. This could be attributed to the fact that the increasing catalyst dosage forces the catalyst's surface to scatter the light and thereby decreasing its activity. Not only that, but agglomeration of catalyst particles is prone to happen which in turns prevents light penetration, all leading to the decrease in the degradation rate and efficiency. Therefore, the catalyst loading should be carefully studied and related to the factor of crystallinity to apply the optimum value for the sake of a decent activity.

2.4 Types of Semiconductors and Choice of ZnO for Photocatalysis

The choice of the photocatalyst is of a high significance and criticality since it's responsible on degrading the toxicants in the wastewater. Semiconductors are either binary (metal oxides and metal sulfides), ternary or quaternary (multicomponent materials) [41], the mostly studied examples of them are represented in Table 2.1

Table 2.1 Different types of photocatalysts used for the removal of pollutants in water [32], [41]

Semiconductors Type		Examples
Binary	Metal Oxides	$TiO_2, ZnO, SnO_2, CeO_2, WO_3, Fe_2O_3...$
	Metal Sulfides	$ZnS, CdS, CuS, Bi_2S_3, MoS_2...$
Ternary		Titanates: $BaTiO_3, SrTiO_3, La_2Ti_2O_3$
		Tungstates: $Bi_2WO_6, ZnWO_4$
Quaternary		$K_2La_2Ti_2O_{10}, NiOK_2Nb_6O_{17}$ $ZnBiVO_4, K_3PW_{12}O_{40}$

- Ternary Semiconductors: They play an important role in many applications as they have very interesting electronic and magnetic properties and possess multiple oxidation states, which will enable them to participate in multiple redox reactions but there are many more miles to go and a search must go on for better and efficient ternary semiconductors [41].

- **Quaternary Semiconductors:** Considerable research attention has been given to quaternary oxide and sulfides because of their exciting photoelectrochemical and photocatalytic properties but very little work has been carried out by researchers on the use of them compared to binary and ternary [41].

Regardless of all of the benefits of ternary and quaternary semiconductors, researchers have focused on the binary semiconductor oxides, as well as this research has, for the following reasons. They're non-toxic, of low cost, photo-chemically active, and they also possess light absorbance properties. These benefits have made them the best option to fill the role in the photocatalysis.

ZnO has been adapted as the photocatalyst in this study. It is a wide band-gap semiconductor with an energy of 3.37eV also with a large excitation binding energy of 60 meV [45]. It's has an excellent degradation competency and it's also relatively cheap and can be synthesized in a simple approach. The quantum efficiency of *ZnO* is very large compared to other metal oxides and it possesses high amounts of active sites [46] thus, it absorbs over a large fraction of the solar spectrum and light quanta rendering it a suitable photocatalyst for usage. It's also important to stress out that its very wide band gap creates some defects in its structure making it less prone to and able to restrain, somewhat, the event of 'electron-hole recombination' that governs the efficiency of the photocatalyst.

Also, since the working pH will be at neutral conditions, and the chosen catalyst should be stable in the water and not emulsify, *ZnO* is a perfect and suitable choice. When the zinc oxides comes in contact with water, zinc hydroxide is formed and according to Degen & Kosec [47], Figure 2.4, the inherent pH where *ZnO* suspension is stable, is at 7.2 as it dissolves in the acidic region and precipitate in the more basic region.

Figure 2.4 Initial and final pH of the zinc oxide solution suspension as a function of time [47].

2.5 Choice of Methylene Blue as the Contaminant

Methylene blue was used as the non-volatile test pollutant, since only a small amount of material will be needed to bring about a striking color change as the dye is photo-oxidized, therefore its degradation will be immediately noticed.

Not only that, but also methylene blue does exist in the produced wastewater as a toxicant so it will make a good model as a pollutant [10].

In addition, the aromatic-like structure of methylene blue renders it as an applicable probe molecule to substitute actual aromatics that could possess a higher toxicity than MB as it was proved that it's only toxic when taken orally so it's relatively safer to work with.

Methylene blue is known for having a high molar absorptivity, meaning that it can absorb light at a given wavelength, which is MB's case $\cong 666 \text{ nm}$ [48].

In photocatalysis, the absorbance at this wavelength is observed to decrease as methylene blue is degraded through the dramatic color change, from blue to colorless, i.e. the oxidation of methylene blue to its intermediate leuco-methylene blue [49] (Figure 2.5).

Figure 2.5 Structures of methylene blue and its colorless reduced form, leuco-methylene blue [49].

2.6 Preparation Techniques of the ZnO Thin Film Photocatalyst

Previous studies have classified the preparation of ZnO thin films into two categories, physical preparation techniques and chemical preparation techniques. Physical methods such as ball milling, magnetron sputtering, and pulsed laser deposition. As for the chemical methods, they make use of all types of chemical reactions such as hydrolysis, precipitation, pyrolysis to prepare photocatalyst particles and thin films. Such as, chemical vapor deposition, chemical solution decomposition, liquid phase deposition, and sol gel [50]. Out of all techniques, sol-gel is the one to be discussed due to its many cons and its process is summarized in Figure 2.6.

Figure 2.6 Schematic representation of the typical sol-gel route [51].

It is a wet chemical technique used for the preparation of either nano-particles or thin film of ZnO either by dip-coating or spin-coating. It's considered as an attractive method for films preparation because of its easy control of the film structure, it's the cheapest and has low fabricating temperature in comparison with other techniques [52].

Controllable parameters include the nature of the precursors, pH, temperature and time of reaction, reagent concentrations, catalyst nature and concentration, aging temperature and time. Thin film photocatalysts, with their high photocatalytic ability, high stability, and convenient reuse, have received more and more attention than nanoparticles, and accordingly, as simple and easy sol-gel dip-coating means, it's one of the versatile methods to prepare thin film-supported photocatalyst [53].

3 EXPERIMENTAL PHOTOCATALYTIC DEGRADATION OF METHYLENE BLUE BY SYNTHESIZED ZnO THIN FILM

This study aims to investigate the photocatalyst material itself. Meaning, an optimized version of ZnO thin films is synthesized by studying and varying parameters that directly influence the catalyst structure, that are ZAD's concentration and the post-heat treatment temperature applied. This consequently also affects its efficiency to serve as a decent photocatalyst and perform a good degradation.

This chapter illustrates the materials and techniques used, the procedure of synthesis of the catalyst film, and it also provides a detailed description of the experimental setup and analytical method used in the photodegradation of methylene blue by the prepared ZnO photocatalyst. Last but not least, the results and discussions regarding the photocatalytic degradation efficiency upon catalyst optimization.

3.1 Materials

- Zinc Acetate Dihydrate (ZAD) (97%), (MW=219.50), from ACROS Organics, Spain.
- 2-Propanol (MW=60.1) from Fisher scientific, U.K.
- Monoethanolamine (MEA), (MW = 61.08), (97%).
- Methylene Blue (MB) powder, (MW=319.86), from Paskem Finechemical Industries, India.
- Standard microscopic glass substrates 75x26 mm, 1 mm thick.
- Deionized water.

3.2 Techniques Used for the Development and Characterization of ZnO Thin Film

The technique used for accurately depositing a liquid thin film of the zinc oxide on a glass substrate was dip-coating and that used for the measuring the absorbance spectrum of the catalyst was the UV-vis spectrometry.

3.2.1 The Dip-Coating Technique

Among the various wet chemical thin film deposition methods dip coating represents the oldest commercially applied coating process. A latest version of the dip-coater was used, it's from HOLMARC Model HO-TH-028, in Figure 3.1. Basically the process may be separated into three important technical stages [54]:

- Immersion & dwell time
- Deposition & drainage
- Evaporation

The dip coater works as follows; to begin with, the glass substrate is lowered down at a constant speed and immersed in the solution precursor, placed in a Teflon beaker, for an amount of time called dwell (dipping) time. Afterwards, as the dipped glass substrate is pulled out, at a constant withdrawal speed with a film of the precursor's sol deposited on it, the excess liquid on the substrate will drain down creating some sort of a thicker layer at the bottom of it due to gravity effect. From this context rises the importance of controlling the withdrawal speed. The higher the speed the more uniform the film is deposited on the glass substrate and the better and higher the thickness is, as illustrated by David Grosso [55], in Figure 3.2. A Teflon beaker cavitated in the dimensions of the glass substrate is used to hold the solution for the reason of not wasting and having to prepare extra sol, that way little volume of sol are capable for the substrate to be dipped in, not needing extra volumes in a normal beaker.

Figure 3.1 Dip-coating unit.

Figure 3.2 Film thickness versus withdrawal speed [55].

At last, pre-heat treatment of the film, for a short period of time, is applied in the chamber where it contains an infra-red heater, that helps in drying the substrate by providing uniform heating to it to evaporate the solvent and dry the film to form the as-deposited thin film. The maximum temperature reached in the chamber is 200°C, and the highest withdrawal speed is at 9 mm/s.

3.2.2 The UV-Vis Spectrometry Technique

The UV-Vis spectrometer is one of the most simplified and economical methods to determine and measure the absorbance range of a chemical species as a function of wavelength. In this research Specord 50 Plus, from analytic-jena-Germany was used to determine the absorbance range of the zinc oxide photocatalyst as well as the change in absorbance of methylene blue upon degradation.

The main components of measurement are present in Figure 3.3.

Figure 3.1 Measurement principle in UV/VIS spectroscopy [56].

This technique is based on the principle of electronic transition in molecules or atoms, which is caused by absorption of light in the UV-vis area that causes electron excitation from ground state to a higher state [57].

The principle is as follows, first a reference sample, a blank, usually water, is put into the transparent non-absorbing cuvette where a light beam passes through it and the intensity of transmitted light is detected. Then, the same procedure is done with the sample to be measured where the transmittance is calculated from the ratio of the sample's transmitted intensity to that of the blank's. And accordingly, the absorbance is then deduced from the negative logarithm of the transmittance value [56].

The next part of the chapter will discuss the film preparation in details explaining the choice of each contributing parameter.

3.3 Synthesis of ZnO Thin Film

As previously discussed, ZnO thin films were prepared in the lab using the sol-gel dip-coating method, and this process could be classified into three main steps:

- Precursor solution preparation
- Deposit of the prepared sol on the substrate by dip-coating
- Post-heat treatment of the film

3.3.1 Preparation of the Solution Precursor (Sol)

The sol-gel is obtained through hydrolysis of the precursor, followed by polymerization-condensation of it to become a gel. Accordingly the choice of precursor, solvent, and additive is highly significant.

3.3.1.1 Opting for a Precursor

Depending on the nature of the molecular precursors, two sol-gel routes are currently used, metal alkoxides in organic solvents or metal salts in aqueous solutions. But currently the sol-gel method implemented is an intermediate between these 2 routes since they use metal salts in alcoholic solutions [58]. Nitrate, chloride, perchlorate, acetylacetonate and alkoxides such as ethoxide and propoxide have been used as zinc precursors but the most often used is acetate dehydrate. Between metal salts and metal alkoxides the choice has always been metal salts. This is due to the fact that they are much less expensive and are not as susceptible to humidity.

On the other hand the debate lies in the metal salts themselves since they are split into inorganic and organic salts. Lamia Znaidi [69] has shown that when nitrates or perchlorates, i.e. inorganic salts, are used as precursors no stable sols could be reproducibly obtained on top of the turbidity and precipitations that occur. Whereas using acetates as precursors makes them serve as stabilizers for the colloidal sol. Their only drawback is that they can be toxic to the gel but they are easily removed in the heat annealing step. Therefore Zinc Acetate Dihydrate ,ZAD, is chosen to be used as a precursor.

3.3.1.2 Opting for a Solvent

ZnO sol-gel is usually carried it in an alcohol that behaves as a solvent (methanol, ethanol, propanol). The choice of a solvent follows mainly 2 criteria:

- Solubility of the chosen precursor in the solvent
- Boiling point of the solvent.

Inorganic salts dissolve in high-polarity solvents, and the dielectric constant of a solvent determines its polarity, therefore a high dielectric constant promotes high solubility of the precursor [60]. Methanol, Ethanol and 2-Propanol have the highest dielectric constants that are 32.66, 24.55, and 19.92 respectively. So from this point of view one can say that methanol shall serve as the best solvent to aid in the sol preparation, but there is still the boiling point criteria to take into consideration.

The solvent should have a boiling point higher than that imposed when heating, making it less volatile so little does it evaporate, and it also has to attain a moderate boiling point that is not too high to not promote cracking of the glass substrate after its dip in the sol and heat treatment in the chamber. Accordingly, the solvent to be chosen is 2-Propanol. It has a good dielectric constant and a boiling temperature of 82.2°C higher than the one that'll be applied for the sol-preparation (70°C).

3.3.1.3 Opting for an Additive

One of the momentous components of *ZnO* sol-gel synthesis is the additive, known as the stabilizer. Some of the most frequent stabilizers used in sol-gel system are the amines of which monoethanolamine (MEA) and diethanolamine (DEA) are among the most prevalent ones. Additives are believed to play the role of chelating and stabilizing ligands, which avoid the rapid precipitation of zinc hydroxide and allow stable dispersions or solutions to be formed [60].

Besides acting as stabilizers, they have roles such as reacting with precursor, facilitating the formation of complexes, being miscible with alcohols and promoting the formation of thin film [61]. In this study the chosen additive, relying on what have been stated earlier, is monoethanolamine (MEA).

Now that the three main parameters have been chosen we move on to the actual sol preparation in the lab. The precursor solution was prepared by using Zinc acetate dohydrate (ZAD) ($Zn(CH_3COO)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$), 2-Propanol (C_3H_8O) and Monoethanolamine (MEA) ($HOCH_2CH_2NH_2$) as starting precursor, solvent and additive respectively. Different sols concentrations of 0.6, 0.2, 0.1, 0.07 and 0.03 mol/l.

These concentrations were first preparede by dissolving the right amount of Zinc acetate dehydrate into a 20 ml solution of 2-Propanol. Knowing the concentration of the wanted sol, it being the same as that of Zn^{2+} , and the solution volume, the following 2 simple rules were used to calculate the required amount of mass to be dissolved.

$$\text{➤ } C_{mol/l} = n_{mol} / V_l \quad (3.1)$$

$$\text{➤ } n_{mol} = m_g / MW_{mol/g} \quad (3.2)$$

The resulted mixture of ZAD and 2-PrOH was then magnetically stirred on a temperature of 50°C for a couple of minutes only to aid the precursor's dissolution in the solvent. Afterwards, the molar ratio $Zn^{2+}:MEA$ was kept 1 throughout the entire experiment and accordingly the required mass of MEA was calculated and added to the mixture.

Then, the homogenous mixture was allowed to stand at a 70°C temperature and stirred for one hour to accelerate the hydrolysis reaction and to obtain a transparent, clear sol. Lastly, the ZnO sols were aged for a period of time that is 24h at room temperature under atmospheric pressure.

3.3.2 Film Deposition of the Prepared Sol on a Glass Substrate by Dip-Coating

As for the dip-coating procedure followed in the lab, it went as follows. For starters, the precursor was poured in a Teflon tube and its place was adjusted in the dip-coater to obtain a full decent dip. Then, the glass substrates were cleaned with soap, distilled water, ethanol and acetone respectively to remove any traces of contaminants that could not be favored for the formation of an appropriate thin layer. They were also dried using a microfiber cloth and if any dust were formed they'd be removed by the edges of paper with gentle scrapping.

Since we're aiming for a single-layered catalyst, the number of dips was set to 1, and when the glass substrate was dipped into the sol the dipping time was adjusted to 7 seconds. The withdrawal speed was set to the maximum of the dip-coater and remained constant at 9 mm/sec to have the thickest film possible, since thicker films provide higher degradation rates.

The moving substrate entrains the liquid in a viscous boundary layer that splits in two at the free surface returning the outer layer to the Teflon beaker and since the solvent is evaporating and draining, the entrained film acquires an approximate wedge shape as shown in Figure 3.4.

Figure 3.2 Film shaping on the substrate with respect to the withdrawal speed [55].

Within the thinning film, the inorganic species are progressively concentrated by evaporation, leading to aggregation, gelation, and final drying to form a type of a dry gel or xerogel [62].

The temperature to aid evaporation of the solvent was set to 150°C, a lot higher than the boiling point of the solvent (82.2°C), so it'll be evaporated completely with a drying duration of 5 minutes.

Post the dip-coating, the synthesized and dipped films should undergo annealing.

The heat treatment, known as post-heat treatment, seems to be the most important factor for promoting crystal-growth and purity increase of *ZnO* film which will help the electron migration through grains and render its recombination, also to remove any traces of organic species and by-products that could be present [63]. It's done in the furnace shown in Figure 3.5 (A).

The annealing temperatures of *ZnO* vary from 200 to 500°C according to A. Zaier [63]. In this study 4 different temperatures were investigated 250, 350 450, and 550°C, to determine the effect of post-heat treatment on the characteristics of *ZnO* microstructure and consequently on its efficiency for photocatalytic degradation.

The procedure is as follows, the fiber glass holding the zinc oxide catalyst, of the most suitable concentration that shall be discussed later, is placed on the ceramic inside the furnace (Figure 3.5 (B)) and allowed to stand there for 1h at the operating temperature.

Figure 3.3 (A): Furnace used for post-heat treatment, (B): Ceramic where the glass substrates were put, in the furnace.

After that, they're left inside of the furnace until it fully cools to avoid sudden breakage of the ceramic upon ultimate shocking decrease in temperature between that of the furnace's and ambient's. The rise of temperature inside the furnace is of a rate 40.424°C as shown in Figure 3.6.

Figure 3.4 A graph showing the rate of increase in the furnace's temperature as a function of time.

The synthesized 1-layer ZnO thin film photocatalyst on a glass substrate is as seen in Figure 3.7.

Figure 3.5 Single layer ZnO thin film photocatalyst substrate.

3.4 Photocatalytic Degradation of Methylene Blue

This part of the chapter shall target the experimental photocatalytic setup, followed by the analytical method used to analyze the degradation rates and lastly the photocatalytic degradation results supported by a detailed analysis and discussion.

3.4.1 Experimental Set-Up and Procedure

The aim of this study is to find the most suitable ZAD (Zn^{2+}) concentration and post heat treatment temperature that favor the highest degradation efficiency, so for the 5 catalyst substrates that represented the 5 investigated concentrations, and the other 4 substrates that took the optimized concentration as a base and studied the effect of the 4 different post-heat treatment temperatures, the following procedure is the same.

To begin with, 42.5 ml of $10\mu\text{mol/l}$ of prepared methylene blue was introduced into a batch photo-reactor followed by placing the ZnO photocatalyst substrate in it. It was adjusted in a way to fully be exposed to the emitted light and efficiently absorb it to promote the redox reactions on its surface as seen in Figure 3.8.

Figure 3.6 A photo taken from the photocatalytic setup for the degradation of MB.

The source of light used was from a UV lamp emitting UV-rays at a wavelength of 365 nm . The overall experimental time was 9h. First, the photo-reactors containing the photocatalyst and methylene blue were left for one hour in the dark to study the effect of the catalyst without the intensity of light on its own.

Afterwards samples from the solutions were taken and introduced in a UV-vis spectrometer to observe the change in the methylene blue absorbance, and from it calculate the initial concentration at $t=0$. From here, the light was turned on and the actual photocatalysis began at room temperature.

The photocatalytic reaction time was 8h, where the degradation of methylene blue was measured through its absorbance at an interval of 30 minutes by taking samples, putting them in a cuvette and in the UV-vis spectrometer to properly monitor the decrease in the absorbance of methylene blue as its being degraded over the 480 minutes.

3.4.2 Analytical Method

The photocatalyzed decolorization process of methylene blue was monitored by recording the absorption spectrum of MB through time intervals. Methylene blue displays a peak at 666 nm, as seen in Figure 3.9, therefore the variation in its absorbance was observed at this wavelength to calculate the change in concentration.

Figure 3.7 Absorption spectra of 10 μ mol/l MB as a function of wavelength.

The photocatalytic degradation kinetics can be described by a pseudo first-order kinetic equation with respect to the concentration of MB, the reaction kinetics are revealed by plotting the natural logarithm of concentration ratio, $\ln(C/C_0)$ where concentration is directly proportional to absorbance so $C/C_0 = A/A_0$, versus the irradiation time, t . The solid lines when plotted indicate that the reaction is of first order kinetics. They are plotted following the equation below [64]:

$$\ln\left(\frac{C_0}{C_t}\right) = -k \cdot t \quad (3.3)$$

Where,

C_0 = Concentration of MB after dark absorption (mol/l).

C_t = Concentration of MB at any given time (mol/l).

t = Irradiation time (minutes).

k = Apparent kinetic constant evaluated from respective logarithmic plots of the experimental data (s^{-1}).

3.4.3 Results and Discussions

The next part of this chapter is dedicated to outline and discuss the repercussions of the studied influencing parameters, had on the out coming photocatalytic degradation results.

3.4.3.1 Optical Absorption of ZnO Photocatalyst

Nine substrates of the ZnO photocatalyst were prepared, five of them referred to the variation in ZAD's concentration, whereas the other four correspond to the variation in the post-heat treatment temperature. The measurement of the absorption spectra of these substrates is highly significant to monitor the increase or decrease in it upon changing parameters that influence the catalyst's surface and structure. The prepared ZnO thin films were measured through the UV-vis spectrometer and were found to have an absorption range between 300-400nm due to the high absorption of ZnO in the UV-A region corresponding to its E_g compatibility with this region.

To further create a hypothesis roaming around the possible influence of alternating the annealing temperatures might have on the photocatalytic degradation, the substrates post-heat treated at 250, 350, 450, and 550°C were measured in the UV-vis machine and the absorption results are shown in Figure 3.10.

Figure 3.8 (A): A graph showing the absorbance (in a.u.) of ZnO photocatalyst annealed at 4 different temperatures, 250, 250, 450, and 550°C, as a function of wavelength (nm), (B): A graph showing the absorbance of ZnO photocatalyst as a function of annealing temperatures at the peak wavelength, 367nm.

The resulting absorbance of the catalyst substrates at different temperatures were very obvious stating that the higher the annealing temperature is, the higher will be the catalyst absorption therefore indicating an improved crystallinity and granular growth of the catalyst particles. Also, it can be observed that the absorption edge for ZnO thin films shifts to longer wavelength, indicating that the band gap for ZnO thin films declines with increasing annealing temperature.

This proposes the postulation of higher degradation rates with higher annealing temperatures. The only opposing factor here is the decrease in absorption as the temperature increased from 450 to 550°C which shall be discussed and illustrated in the next part of the chapter.

3.4.3.2 The Influence of ZnO (Zn^{2+}) Concentration on the Photocatalytic Degradation Efficiency

ZnO dosage has a huge impact in influencing the degradation rate, it has been reported in a series of studies that the higher the concentration of the catalyst, the more active sites shall be present, therefore promoting an efficient degradation [65].

On the other hand, there is a limit to the increase in concentration since it could lead to the inhibition of the photocatalysis for reasons that will be discussed throughout this part. Accordingly, studying the effect of concentration is of a high interest.

ZnO photocatalyst substrates of concentrations 0.03, 0.07, 0.1, 0.2, and 0.6M post-heat treated at 350°C as an optimum annealing temperature, for now [66], were investigated.

Following the analytical method mentioned before, the photocatalytic degradation rates of applying these five different catalyst concentrations were calculated and plotted from the decrease in the methylene blue concentration as shown in Figure 3.11.

Figure 3.9 Degradation kinetics of Methylene Blue by 0.03, 0.07, 0.1, 0.2, and 0.6M of Zinc Oxide.

To avoid the use of a catalyst excess, it is necessary to identify the optimum loading for an efficient removal of the contaminants. So it is necessary to optimize the amount of catalyst with respect to the highest photocatalytic activity.

The progress of the conversion is linear up to 0.1M while for further increase of catalyst amount, the conversion stabilizes. As the concentration of the zinc oxide catalyst kept on increasing from 0.03 to 0.1M, the reaction rates were proportional to it and the higher the catalyst dosage was, the better was the degradation of methylene blue to carbon dioxide and water.

The hypothesis of ‘As the catalyst concentration increases, the photocatalytic degradation rate increases too’ could be attributed to the fact that an increased loading of catalyst increases the available active sites on the surface of contact between the catalyst particles and the methylene blue, consequently the quantity of photons adsorbed shall be greater, thus promoting the increase in the creation of hydroxyl radicals and superoxide ions and lastly increasing the photocatalytic degradation.

The photocatalytic degradation efficiency enhanced by 35% with the increase in catalyst dosage from 0.03 to 0.1M, and the efficiencies were obtained through the following formula [67], and shown in Figure 3.12.

$$\text{Degradation Efficiency } \eta \text{ (\%)} = \frac{C_0 - C_f}{C_0} \times 100 \quad (3.4)$$

Figure 3.10 A histogram showing the photocatalytic degradation efficiencies upon using 5 different concentrations of ZnO, 0.03, 0.07, 0.1, 0.2, 0.6M.

On the other hand, further increase in the catalyst concentration from 0.1 to 0.2 and then 0.6M limits the credibility of the proposed hypothesis since the trend of the degradation efficiencies of methylene blue were inversely proportional to the increase in concentration since the degradation efficiency declined by 10%.

To explain this phenomenon, one should first be aware that the surface of the catalyst is the foundation for an effective photocatalytic degradation since it's where the light penetrate and pollutants interact.

To begin with, a further increase in the catalyst concentration above 0.1M may have contributed in increasing the opacity of the solution that on the other hand decreases the amount of photons penetration that are responsible of creating the electron-hole pair, and thereby decreasing the photocatalytic degradation rate.

In addition, the suspended catalyst particles may have been responsible on light scattering, thereby reducing the rate of degradation.

Also, a considerable factor could be that the number of methylene blue molecules present might have not been sufficient enough to adsorb to that much huge amount of ZnO particles.

Not only that, but also when the catalyst was present in more amounts than needed, agglomerates might have formed, similar to those observed in the SEM done by Singh, D K, et al. [68]. Meaning, particles at the surface of the catalyst would interact together leaving an unoccupied space between each agglomerate and the other.

This could've lead to the loss of active sites on the catalyst's surface and also promoted the electron-hole recombination due to the fact that the electron might not have been able to smoothly jump from one particle to the other so it had to recombine again, rendering the photocatalytic degradation to inhibition.

As a results to what have been discussed and analyzed, 0.1M of zinc oxide photocatalyst is considered the optimal concentration in this situation, and one can say it's the limit to saturation. Since according to these data, its surface is the surface that's completely exposed to radiation therefore it has the highest amount of active sites on its surface promoting a decent and efficient degradation of methylene blue.

3.4.3.3 The Influence of ZnO Post-heat Treatment Temperature on the Photocatalytic Degradation Efficiency

Following the determination of the optimum catalyst concentration for an efficient photocatalytic degradation, a 0.1M *ZnO* thin film was thermally treated at 4 different temperatures that are, 250, 350, 450, and 550°C.

This approach was decided to be taken upon to study how the variation in post-heat treatment temperatures affect the microstructure of the catalyst, in terms of photocatalytical properties, surface decontamination and the consequent particle change regarding crystallinity, and how that in return influences the photocatalytic degradation rates and efficiencies.

The photocatalytic degradation kinetics resulting from post-heat treating at 250, 350, and 450, 550°C and shown in Figure 3.13.

Figure 3.11 Degradation kinetics of Methylene Blue by 0.1 M Zinc Oxide annealed at 250, 350, 450, and 550 °C.

The increase in the post-heat treatment temperature of the *ZnO* substrates with an interval of 100°C from 250 to 350 then 450°C consequently enhanced its photocatalytic activity by raising the degradation efficiencies from 74.40% to 84.54% then 88.82% respectively.

This increase in the degradation is owed to the enhanced microstructural properties of the photocatalyst itself, therefore one should decompose what's happening in the catalyst into a series of stages upon annealing.

To begin with, the catalyst's surface is being decontaminated as the temperature is increased from 250 to 350°C, thus active sites are recovered from the contaminants and the catalyst's surface is cleaner and contains pure *ZnO*. To further address this, according to Baruah and Dutta [66], the catalyst's surface at 250°C still contains basic zinc acetate where the carboxylate groups settle on a part of the particles surface reducing the availability of active sites that promote photocatalytic degradation.

Whereas when the annealing temperature was increased to 350°C, decarboxylation occurs and basic zinc acetate decomposes to its oxide leading to the formation of *ZnO* nanocrystallites with a cleaner, more pure and with higher active sites for the photocatalysis to occur at.

Further increase of annealing temperature to reach 450°C resulted in a similar increase in the degradation efficiency for the following reasons. The electron-hole creation and recombination is the main element for either a horrendous or successful photocatalytic degradation, thus the primary purpose is to promote its creation and electron migration, and inhibit the recombination.

With increasing the annealing temperature up to 450°C, the oxygen content might have decreased by diffusing from its lattice, thereby creating oxygen vacancies in the film and introducing some defects to the band gap and consequently decreasing the band gap itself [69]. To further illustrate, when the oxygen vacancies were created and decreased the band gap energy, the electron-hole pair creation has become much easier and facilitated since the distance electrons have to travel from the valence band to the conduction band is now lower.

Even though the electron-hole creation is now much more likely to happen than at lower post-heat treatment temperatures but it's a double-edged weapon, since the recombination is still an option especially because the band gap energy is now lower. Therefore, here comes the role of the surface crystallinity.

For the created electron to help promote a good photocatalysis, it should be able to migrate through the catalyst particles very easily so that it doesn't have to recombine. As the annealing temperature was increased to 450°C, the size of crystal grains increased and that is attributed to Ostwald ripening effect, which is granular growth. This reduces the pores on the surface of the films and renders it to be more homogeneous with better coverage, consequently the particle grains are well aligned, positioned and adhered on the glass substrate thereby improving the catalyst's crystallinity. Therefore, electrons are free to properly migrate through the crystal interconnected grains and initiate the photocatalysis.

In a nutshell, it is found that crystallinity is the most important factor that influences the photocatalytic performance as *ZnO* with higher crystallinity exhibited larger degradation efficiencies. A study done by Varnamkhasti et al. [70] of *ZnO* thin films annealed at 250, 350, and 450°C showed similar results to this research and their SEM is worth seeing to better visualize the effect of increasing post-heat treatment temperatures on the crystallinity and grain growth on the catalyst's surface.

On the other hand, the expected continuous increase in the kinetics rate and degradation efficiencies of methylene blue with the increase in annealing temperature now lack congruence. The degradation rate constant decreased upon temperature increase from 450 to 550°C and can be observed in Figure 3.14

Figure 3.12 A histogram showing the degradation rate constants upon using ZnO photocatalyst annealed at 250, 350, 450, 550 °C.

This could be attributed to the fact that this further increase of a 100°C to reach 550°C may have caused the crystallinity to be disturbed as the ZnO particles might have formed agglomerates thereby reducing the surface area of contact and that for electron migration [69]. Not only that, but a reason worth mentioning is that the silica in the glass substrate could have impregnated in the zinc oxide film and caused a disorder in crystallinity which promotes a decline in its efficiency.

It could also be referred to the influence of this high temperature might have had on the support fiber glass substrate of the catalyst. Since beyond 450°C the fiber might slowly start to soften and can be prone to failure in a relatively short time which will decline the kinetics of the photocatalytic degradation [71].

In the course of the procedure of sampling into the UV-vis spectrometer to monitor the absorbance of methylene blue during the photocatalytic degradation, the fading in the methylene blue color began to become noticeable, and after that the experimental time of 480 minutes have passed, the photo-degradation of methylene blue was observed by the naked eye as seen in Figure 3.15.

Figure 3.13 Change in color of methylene blue prior and post degradation by 0.1M ZnO thin film annealed at different temperatures.

CONCNLUSION AND FUTURE PERSPECTIVES

Produced wastewater from the oil and gas industries is detrimental to human and marine health as well as for the ecosystem on a general note. A naïve human would suggest to simply discharge the PWW elsewhere disregarding that it has high potential to be polished and treated to become as pure as fresh water. This approach is of high significance since with the increasing population, more countries are becoming water stressed. For this reason, researchers have investigated the advanced oxidation processes as the route for a clean water source. The hydroxyl radicals and superoxide ions are capable of reducing and oxidizing the contaminants into non-toxic end species. From here, photocatalysis is implemented, not to extract, separate or remove, but to destroy and degrade toxicants.

This innovative, highly effective and relatively cheap technology was conducted by this research and was done at the Lab of Petroleum in the Lebanese University, Faculty of Engineering. This work focuses on the synthesis, optimization and development of the heterogeneous photocatalytic degradation of methylene blue by zinc oxide thin films deposited on a glass substrate. Optimization of the catalyst thin film was done by two approaches. The first one aimed to observe the influence of changing the catalyst's concentration on its properties and how these properties in turn affected the degradation efficiencies where 0.1M emerged as the optimum concentration for an excellent photocatalytic performance. Whereas, the second approach took the optimized concentration and focused on varying the annealing temperatures that in turn changed the microstructure of the catalyst. The most appealing post-heat treatment temperature that showed the highest degradation efficiency was 450°C.

As for future perspectives, this optimized zinc oxide catalyst could be further improved by doping with metals. This route allows for a much better degradation due to the decrease in the band gap energy it proposes and thereby inhibiting the recombination of electrons. In addition, layering could be employed to observe the effect of thickness on the microstructure of the catalyst and thereby on the photocatalytic degradation. Also, the photoactivity of this *ZnO* semiconductor could be observed under sunlight instead of UV, which could be of a huge importance since zinc oxide is known to be very efficient under sunlight and to economic reasons, since sunlight is free and abundant.

But the most promising route might be by coupling the investigated work in this research with another advanced oxidation process such as Fenton process, which will lead to a reliable treatment of wastewater to become polished and thus open doors for a world that has no scarcity in fresh water, but an excess.

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